

Human Capital Development and Poverty Alleviation in Nigeria: Evidence from ARDL Model

Omolara Campbell, PhD and Toluwalope Ogunro, PhD

Department of Economics and Development Studies,

Lead City University, Ibadan, Oyo State, Nigeria

Email: *omolaracampbell@yahoo.com (O. C.); rehobotty@gmail.com (T. O.)*

Abstract

Theoretical and empirical research has emphasized that education is the most powerful instrument for developing and empowering citizens to master their social, cultural environment and compete for survival. However, most of the developing economies, although conscious of the transformation, that education brings, are yet to reap its full potential. A recent statistic on the multidimensional poverty index in Nigeria coordinated by the National Bureau of Statistics (2022) indicates that 63% of persons living in Nigeria (133 million people) are multidimensionally poor. Furthermore, the incidence of monetary poverty is lower than the incidence of multidimensional poverty across most states. The 2018/19 national monetary poverty line indicates that 40.1% of people are poor. Over time, different governments in Nigeria have adopted programmes and policies to address the challenge of poverty in Nigeria, some of which are based on the empowerment of youths and women, among others. Also, education at the primary level in most states in Nigeria is financed by the government. This study ascertains whether human capital development can alleviate the poverty level of Nigerians using data that spans from 1985-2020. The autoregressive distributed lag model was employed. It was found that a long-run relationship exists between human capital development and poverty in Nigeria. In the short run, government spending on health, consumer price index, final consumption expenditure and employed persons determine poverty headcount in Nigeria. Even though findings indicate significant relationships between key variables, the study recommends the urgent need to ensure that economic growth is inclusive and sustainable in Nigeria. This can be enhanced through increased public and private sector investment in education and health.

Keywords: Human capital development, poverty, government health expenditure, consumption expenditure and consumer price index

Introduction

Many researchers over the decades have confirmed the assertion that humans are the most important and potential source of productivity.

Economies have made appreciable economic progress accompanied by steady increases in economic growth via the persistent increase in capacity to train productive and skilled workers

(Dixit *et al*, 2017). All these are required to manipulate capital, technology and land, among other things, in order to produce goods and services for human consumption. Related to this, human capital has been defined as “the abilities and skills of human resources” (Adelakun, 2011). It is, therefore, the foundation and the end of any form of capital. Each of the integrals of human capital, education, and health has been proven to have a remarkable impact on economic growth. For instance, education has a strong impact on labour productivity, the rate of innovation, healthy living and technological improvements. It is beneficial to humans because it decreases inequality, improves the quality of life and, more importantly, it is a factor in increasing the income level of individuals (Campbell, 2021). Increased labour productivity translates to increased wages, and improved access to health facilities, which ultimately leads to economic growth and general improvement of the aggregate living standard. Human development raises capacities and, consequently creativity and productivity of economic agents who make critical contributions to economic growth. It leads to labour quality, whose impact on economic growth is widely taken care of by investment in human capital (Campbell, 2021). The assumption is that an individual with better skills acquired from education and training has more choices and opportunity of getting a good job and do good business, thereby increasing his income level. This explains the importance of human capital for poverty reduction in developing countries. Furthermore, the higher the level of productivity, the higher the returns that accrue. The economic

progress of East Asian countries has been noted in the literature to be primarily due to investment in education.

Davis and Sanchez-Martinez (2014) adopt the World Bank definition of poverty to imply deprivation in well-being. This includes low incomes, inability to acquire basic goods and services necessary for survival, poor health outcomes, low levels of education, poor access to clean water and sanitation among others. In absolute terms, poverty implies a lack of basic amenities (food, housing, health care), while in relative terms, poor people have income below the benchmark in a community average, making it difficult for affected people to enjoy a decent life. The empirical literature has also confirmed that poverty is negatively linked with an income level of the household. So, higher wages imply low poverty. A World Bank Report puts it that most people in the world live in poverty. According to the statistics, about 85% of the world population lives on less than \$30 per day, about two-thirds survive on less than \$10 per day, while about every tenth person lives on less than \$1.90 per day (World Population Growth, 2021). This implies that no country or continent is actually free from poverty. However, the rate varies. Nigeria has been rated as one of the poorest countries in the world. A recent statistic on the multidimensional poverty index in Nigeria coordinated by the National Bureau of Statistics (2022) indicates that 63% of persons living in Nigeria (133 million people) are multidimensionally poor. Furthermore, the incidence of monetary poverty is lower than the incidence of multidimensional poverty across

most states. The 2018/19 national monetary poverty line indicates that 40.1% of people are poor. Furthermore, a recent Longitudinal Phone Survey (NLPS) indicate that the welfare status of Nigerians post-COVID-19 and their response to incessant insurgencies ravaging the six geopolitical zones in Nigeria have possible tendencies of pushing about additional 10 million Nigerians into abject poverty.

The high rate of poverty across the globe, especially in Sub-Saharan Africa, is of great concern to the United Nations (UN). This explains why in the year 2000, the UN led a global effort to tackle poverty by kickstarting the Millennium Development Goals (MDGs), with the first goal as “to eradicate extreme poverty across the globe by 2015.” The MDGs were not fully realized and thus were replaced by the 17 Sustainable Development Goals, meant to end poverty, ensure prosperity and protect the planet by 2030. Surprisingly, despite the acknowledged importance of human capital development, the developing countries of sub-Saharan Africa (SSA), especially Nigeria, still lag behind other regions in human capital development, with the gap widening over time. The country continues to be faced with high levels of extreme poverty, a high annual population growth rate, a life expectancy that is among the lowest in the world, and a very low youth literacy rate

Successive government administrations at various times implemented different chains of policies and programmes such as Operation Feed the Nation, Rural Banking Scheme and Austerity Measures by Olusegun Obasanjo's administration, 1976-1979; the Green Revolution

by Shehu Shagari in 1980; War Against Indiscipline and Corruption by General Muhammadu Buhari in 1983; the establishment of Peoples Bank, Directorate of Foods Roads and Rural Infrastructure (DFRRI), Nigerian Agricultural Land Development Authority (NALDA), National Directorate of Employment (NDE) and Family Support Program (FSP) by Babangida administration, 1986-1993; Family Economic Advancement Programme (FEAP) by the administration of Late General Sani Abacha in 1997; National Poverty Eradication Program (NAPEP) of 1999; and National Economic Empowerment and Development Strategy 1 and 2 (NEEDS). A more recent one is the N-Power programme of President Muhammadu Buhari's administration. These were all aimed at improving the economic and social conditions of the unprotected part of the population to reduce the level of severe poverty in the country. It is not clear if these policies have yielded any remarkable reduction in the country's poverty profile amidst increasing public spending, thus, prompting the question of whether any relationship exists between human capital and poverty in Nigeria.

Considering the latest multidimensional poverty index of Nigeria, and the fact that human capital development improves capabilities and increases the productivity of the working population, it becomes imperative to investigate whether an investment in human beings via the integrals of human capital can actually alleviate poverty in Nigeria using data that spans from 1985-2020. To this end, following this introduction is the review of theories, the link

between human capital development and poverty, the methodology adopted for the study, empirical results of the study, the conclusion and recommendations.

Human Capital Theory

This theory attempts to answer the question of “Why the decision to invest in education is made?” The theory is, therefore, relevant at the decision-making stages. The proponents of this theory (Theodore Schultz, 1961; Garry Becker, 1967) see human capital as how education increases the productivity and efficiency of workers by increasing the level of their cognitive skills. In other words, they see human capital as the stock of economically productive human capabilities, which can be formed by combining innate abilities with investments in human beings. Examples of such assets include expenditures on education, on-the-job training, health and nutrition. Such expenditures increase future productive capacity at the expense of current consumption. The provision of education is seen as a productive investment in human capital, an investment which the proponents of the human capital theory consider to be equally worthwhile than that in physical capital. The notion of education as a capital good is rooted in this concept of human capital, which attached a high premium to human skills as a factor of production in the development process. Human skill or productivity has been found by this theory to be an important input in the process of development as finance, natural wealth, and physical plant. The proponents of the theory have established that basic literacy enhances the

productivity of workers in low skilled occupations. In this regard, an instruction that demands logical or analytical reasoning, or provides technical and specialized knowledge, increases the marginal productivity of workers in high-skill or professional positions. Thus, educational choices may be assimilated into investment decisions where rational individuals decide on the optimal amount of education they wish to acquire so as to maximize the net return on education. The higher the provision of schooling, the greater the stock of human capital in society. Consequently, the greater the increases in national productivity and economic growth.

Additional schooling, however, is expected to generate benefits in terms of enhanced future earnings but also entail costs: direct as well as opportunity cost resulting from delayed entry into the labour market. It is also noteworthy that the human-capital theory contends that education participation/enrolment is an investment decision by which individuals forgo time and resources in return for higher wages in future. People invest in education due to the consideration they have given to the future earnings streams that will result. From these submissions, it would be possible for individuals or households to build up human capital by investing in education with the expectation of deriving some satisfactory future benefits. Incidentally, such help would include increased earnings, heightened social status, and higher economic prestige associated with higher educational qualifications such as first, second and doctorate degrees. It can be inferred from

the foregoing submissions that basic literacy enhances the productivity of workers in low-skill occupations. Furthermore, instruction that demands logical or analytical reasoning, or provides technical and specialized knowledge, increases the marginal productivity of workers in high-skill or professional positions.

Classical Poverty Theory

This theory was proposed by Lewis (1961) using Mexico and Puterico as case studies. The theory explains poverty in terms of the conditions under which the poor lives i.e. unemployment, underdevelopment, poor education and poor health. The theory emphasizes the relationship between income and productivity. Other researchers have also contributed to this theory. For instance, Shaffer (2008) explains poverty in terms of lack or inadequate incentive system to realize an individual's capabilities, the nature of economic underdevelopment and much more.

Human Capital Development and Poverty

Policymakers and academicians have long viewed human capital development via its integrals as a vital tool for economic growth and poverty reduction in any nation. Current projections assume that Sub-Saharan Africa cannot achieve the sustainable development goal of reducing extreme poverty to less than 3% unless income inequality is reduced drastically through more inclusive growth (Makuta and O'Hare, 2015). The key to poverty reduction and economic development, according to Philbin (1996), involves the ability of a nation to engage in an adequate capacity building, which has to do

with improving people's cognitive and non-cognitive abilities and their health. This involves developing and strengthening the skills, knowledge, abilities and resources that organizations and communities need to survive, adapt, and thrive in the fast-changing world. These qualities affect the possibilities of earning current and future money income. The assumption is that the higher the productivity of an individual, the higher the returns that accrue.

Poverty and human capital have been expressed in literature to possess a 2-way causal relationship. For instance, poverty is seen as hindering the accumulation of human capital. Zhang (2014) puts it that due to the high costs of education in Western China, low-income households are prevented from accessing education. This perpetuates the poverty trap. Credit constraints have also been found to have a negative effect on human capital accumulation, especially for poor households (Hai and Heckman, 2017). The works of Hong and Pandey (2007), Arias, Gimenz and Sanchez (2016) employed the Logistic and Probit Models respectively to show that human capital reduces the likelihood of an individual being poor.

Analyzing time series data through descriptive analytical techniques, empirical studies of Ali, Ahmad et al (2013) Janjua and Kamal (2014), and David *et al.* (2018) submit that human capital has a negative impact on poverty levels in developing countries. Sustaining growth and making it inclusive requires innovative solutions and efficient investments in human capital development. Developing and utilizing education skills, health,

and other forms of acquired knowledge serve as a crucial determinant of a nation's productivity and standard of living. This is excessively illustrated by the outstanding records of Japan, Taiwan, Hong Kong, South Korea, and other fast-growing Asian economies as most of them lack natural resources, which is believed to be a major determinant of economic performance. Nevertheless, these nations have managed to experience significant, extreme and rapid economic growth and development because they have had a well-trained, educated, healthy and hard-working labour force.

Methodology of the Study

This study makes use of both descriptive and inferential statistics to capture the nature of the relationship existing between human capital development and poverty in Nigeria.

Model Specification

With reference to the study of Anyanwu (2013) that examined the correlates of economic growth for poverty reduction in Nigeria, this study specifies a regression model where poverty is dependent on human capital development and other explanatory variables. Equation (1) is a growth model that shows that poverty is a function of GDP growth rate, and primary school enrolment, among other variables.

The model is modified to incorporate other variables identified in the literature to determine poverty.

Where: pov = poverty headcount; gdpg = gross domestic product growth rate; pse = primary school enrolment; gxh = government

expenditure on health; fce = final consumption expenditure; emp = persons employed; cpi = consumer price index; and t = time.

Equation one can be captured econometrically in functional form, and the model is expressed in equation (2):

$$pov_t = (gdpg_t, pse_t, gxh_t, cpi_t, fce_t, emp_t) \quad (1)$$

The autoregressive distributed lag model expressed in equation (3) is a long-run cointegration and bounds test. Δ is a difference operator, $\beta_1, \beta_2, \beta_3, \beta_4, \beta_5, \beta_6$ are measures in the short term, $\delta_1, \delta_2, \delta_3, \delta_4, \delta_5, \delta_6$ measure long run relationship and v_t is the error term. To measure cointegration, the null hypothesis states that: H_0 :

$$\delta_1 = \delta_2 = \delta_3 = \delta_4 = \delta_5 = \delta_6 = 0$$

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta pov_t = & \beta_0 + \sum_{i=1}^k \beta_1 \Delta pov_{t-i} + \sum_{i=1}^l \beta_2 \Delta pse_{t-i} + \\ & \sum_{i=1}^m \beta_3 \Delta gdpg_{t-i} + \sum_{i=1}^n \beta_4 \Delta gxh_{t-i} + \sum_{i=1}^o \beta_5 \Delta cpi_{t-i} \quad (3) \\ & \sum_{i=1}^p \beta_6 \Delta fce_{t-i} + \sum_{i=1}^q \beta_6 \Delta emp_t + \delta_1 pov_{t-1} + \delta_2 pse_{t-1} + \\ & \delta_3 gdpg_{t-1} + \dots + v_t \end{aligned}$$

The analysis of error correction model is represented using equation (4) below:

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta pov_t = & \alpha_0 + \sum_{i=1}^n \beta_i \Delta pov_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^y \gamma_i \Delta gdpg_{t-i} + \\ & \sum_{i=0}^z \theta_i \Delta gxg_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^w \eta_i cpi_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^v \chi_i fce_{t-i} + \\ & \sum_{i=0}^u \lambda_i \Delta emp_t + \varphi ecm_{t-i} + v_t \quad (4) \end{aligned}$$

Sources of Data

The research employed time-series data from the period of 1985 to 2020 for each variable, such as Poverty (Poverty headcount ratio at \$1.90 a day 2011 PPP % of the population), primary school

enrolment rate, gross domestic product growth rate, log of government expenditure on health, log of final consumption expenditure, log of employed population and consumer price index. The time series data are derived from various secondary sources such as the Central Bank of Nigeria Statistical Bulletin, the National Bureau of Statistics (NBS) and the World Development Indicators (WDI). The data gathered were subjected to various econometric tests with the aid of E-views.

Empirical Result and Discussion

The empirical estimation commences with a unit root test to confirm the stationarity level of the variables understudied using the Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) approach. The need to understudy the stationarity test becomes imperative since many macroeconomic series usually exhibit non-stationarity at the level (Granger, 1981). This, therefore, makes the estimation outputs spurious. The result of the ADF estimator at a 5% level of significance is presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Test of Unit Root in the Variables

Variables	Augmented Dickey Fuller (ADF) Test				Decision
	@ Level		@ First difference		
	t-statistic	P-value (5%)	t-statistic	P-value (5%)	
pov	-1.860	0.654	-7.6811	0.00*	I(1)
pse	-3.27	0.024*	-	-	I(0)
gdp	-3.04	0.136	-5.01	0.002*	I(1)
lnfce	-4.91	0.002*	-	-	I(0)
lngh	2.93	1.00	-6.7	0.00*	I(1)
lnemp	-1.029	0.73	-5.83	0.00*	I(1)
cpi	-3.38	0.01*	-	-	I(0)

Note: (*) indicates significance at 5%

Source: Authors Computation (2022)

Following the unit root test result reported in Table 1, the outcome shows that we do not accept the null hypotheses of a unit root in primary school enrolment, consumer price index, and final consumption expenditure at a 5% significance level. It implies that the series (i.e. primary school enrolment, consumer price index, and final consumption expenditure) are stationary at levels, i.e. I(0). However, the alternative hypothesis that there is no unit root in employment, government expenditure on health, GDP growth rate and poverty is rejected at the

conventional level. Afterwards, the stationarity test of the economic variables was conducted at the first difference, and the results show the non-acceptance of the null hypotheses of unit root at a 5% level of significance. Therefore, the variables -employment, government expenditure on health, GDP growth rate and poverty are found stationary at first difference, i.e. I(1). Based on the stationarity test result of the variables found to exhibit both I(0) and I(1) features, the autoregressive distributed lag (ARDL) bound approach is found to be the most appropriate

estimation method to estimate the relationship between human capital development and poverty in Nigeria. Table 2 provides the bound test for the cointegration between human capital development and poverty in Nigeria.

Table 2: Bounds test for Cointegration

F-Statistic (pov, pse, gdp, lnfc, lngxh, lnemp, cpi)	3.920088*		
Critical values	1%	5%	10%
Lower Bound I(0)	3.15	2.45	2.12
Upper Bound I(1)	4.43	3.61	3.23

Note: (*) shows significance and rejection of no cointegration of null hypothesis at 5% level

Source: Authors' computation (2022)

According to the estimated bound result in Table 2, the F-statistics of 3.92 is greater than the upper bound of 3.61 at 5% significance level. It implies that there is a cointegration among poverty, primary school enrolment rate, gross domestic product growth, government expenditure on health, final consumption expenditure, employed persons, and consumer price index. Thus, this means that there is a long-run relationship between poverty, primary school enrolment rate, gross domestic product growth rate, government expenditure on health, final consumption expenditure, employed persons, and consumer price index in Nigeria. The economic implication is that there is a long-run relationship between human capital development and the poverty rate in the Nigerian economy within the period of 1985-2020.

The long-run and short-run estimates for all the explanatory variables are presented in Table 3. Following the long-run estimates, the result shows that government health expenditure has a direct and significant impact on poverty reduction. This is empirical evidence that government spending on health has not been able

to curtail the number of poor people in the country. It, therefore, means the current government expenditure on healthcare facilities and services does not have the capability of reducing the average number of people living below US\$1.90/day. Notably, the reason is not farfetched since the country's national budget on health falls below 5% of the total budget over the year against at least 15% of the yearly national budget to the health sector proposed by African leaders at the Abuja declaration in 2001 and World Health Organization (WHO, 2014). It should be noted here that there is strong evidence in the literature that provision of good health across the population significantly contributes to labour and human capital that achieve economic growth and, ultimately individual's income and well-being (Hsiao and Heller, 2007). However, the coefficients of primary school enrolment, GDP growth, final consumption expenditure, employment and consumer price index are not significant statistically at the 5% level.

Table 3: ARDL Result

Dependent Variable: Poverty			
Long run Estimates			
Variables	Coefficient	Std. Error	T statistic
pse	-1.067	0.72	-1.48
gdpg	-0.08	0.945	-0.08
lnfce	-1.32	0.96	-1.38
lngxh	12.79	6.04	2.12**
lnemp	-21.96	25.99	-0.84
cpi	0.04	0.23	0.19
Short run Estimates			
$\Delta(\text{poverty}(-1))$	0.36	0.12	2.93**
$\Delta(\text{fce})$	-0.17	0.09	-1.89*
$\Delta(\text{lngxh})$	0.39	1.30	0.30
$\Delta(\text{lngxh}(-1))$	-3.94	0.98	-4.04***
$\Delta(\text{lngxh}(-2))$	-4.93	1.12	-4.39***
$\Delta(\text{gdpg})$	-0.18	0.17	-1.05
$\Delta(\text{gdpg}(-1))$	0.43	0.18	-2.41**
$\Delta(\text{gdpg}(-2))$	0.35	0.22	1.63
$\Delta(\text{cpi})$	-0.13	0.06	-2.14
$\Delta(\text{cpi}(-1))$	0.09	0.04	2.27**
$\Delta(\text{cpi}(-2))$	0.11	0.05	2.12**
$\Delta(\text{emp})$	131	32.93	3.98***
$\Delta(\text{emp}(-1))$	-319	46.92	-6.80***
ECT(-1)	-0.47	0.07	-6.41***
C	204	31.04	6.59*
R- squared	0.84	Serial correlation	Prob. =0.24
Adjusted R-squared	0.72	Heteroskedasticity	Prob. =0.39
F statistic	6.93	Normality	0.002
Durbin-Watson	2.68		

Note: (***; **; *) significant at 1%, 5% and 10% respectively

Source: Authors' computation (2022).

As regards the short-run estimates, findings show that the lagged value of poverty at one is positive and significant at 5%, which implies that poverty can be reinforcing and may not be minimized in the short run. With respect to final consumption expenditure, its parameter estimate is negative and significant to the poverty level at 10%. Specifically, an increase in final consumption expenditure in the current period

reduces poverty by 17%. The study concludes that final consumption expenditure has a reducing effect on poverty in the short run, as higher final consumption expenditure is an indication of an improved welfare level. Similarly, the first and second lags of government health expenditure have negative coefficients, which are significant statistically at the 1% level. However, lag one of GDP growth

is found to be significant and positive to poverty. This means that there is a likelihood that the growth rate of the national income is insufficient to reduce poverty. More so, the highly volatile nature of the major income-earning sector of the Nigerian economy could inform its ineffectiveness in poverty reduction.

The consumer price index in the current period shows a negative relationship with poverty headcount, while one and two lagged values of the consumer price index are positive and significant to increase poverty headcount. A positive relationship is expected between the consumer price index and poverty as it reduces disposable income thereby increasing the number of people experiencing poverty as there is a fall in the purchasing power of money. This is reflected in the first and second lagged values of the consumer price index as an increase in the consumer price index increases poverty headcount by 9% and 11%, respectively.

Logged values of employed persons in the current period show a positive and significant relationship with poverty in the short run, while lag one of the variables shows a negative relationship with poverty. The study by Dusun and Ogunleye (2016) found that employment is not significant to poverty reduction, necessitating further examination of the employment capability of the productive sectors of the economy that aid poverty reduction. According to Ajakaiye et al. (2016), agriculture contributed more to employment, estimated at above 50%. Unfortunately, this sector is subject to persistent insurgencies or insecurities, which can discourage investment in the sector. The attacks

by herdsmen on farm owners and the crisis in the northern part of Nigeria can scare people from investing and working in the sector. The informal sector employs more people, with a high level of uncertainty hence unstable income flow; also, the fall in the oil price, which is a major export product of Nigeria, has an impact on GDP and employment variables in Nigeria.

The error correction term is negative, significant and less than one, signifying that if there is a disequilibrium in the model, the speed of adjustment to equilibrium is 47%. The diagnostic tests examined are serial correlation, heteroscedasticity and normality; while there are no challenges with serial correlation and heteroscedasticity, the error term is not normally distributed.

Conclusion and Recommendations

This study presented the analysis of human capital development and poverty relationship in Nigeria. Empirical analysis using time series data over the period 1985- 2020 shows that government spending on health has a positive relationship with poverty in the long run, an indication that government spending on health is not sufficient to reduce poverty in the country in the long run. The employment variable in the current period has a reducing effect on poverty. However, the employing sector can determine the extent to which poverty is reduced. There is a need to address the unemployment problem being faced in the country since employment guarantees income and could directly cause a decline in poverty. Employment schemes that support entrepreneurship, informal sector

training and the development of human capital can enhance human capital development.

Several initiatives on human capital development will be a step in the right direction to fight against poverty and social exclusion in Nigeria. There is an urgent need for the alignment of existing curricula and the development of new curricula for tertiary institutions to match the needs of the manufacturing sector in research and innovation. This will, without a doubt, drive the structural transformation of the economy. Focusing on job-creating and broad-based growth cannot be overemphasized. Giving all citizens due consideration for improved quality of public services and efficiency as measured by the incidence of public spending should be revisited by the government. There is also the need for support safety nets to protect citizens against economic and social shocks. Improving access to education, nutrition and health in Nigeria need urgent attention, given that the United Nations and World Health Organization have a benchmark on budgetary allocation to health and the United Nations Educational Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNICEF) benchmark of 26% budgetary allocation to education. All these measures will drive structural transformation in the form of reallocation of economic activity to the manufacturing sector of the Nigerian economy, which presently is at a low level of performance. Above all, poverty reduction among the citizenry will be achieved.

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